

Nitric Oxide Synthase (NOS) Assay Kit Instruction

A014-2 Total NOS Assay

I. Principle of the Kit

NOS catalyze the production of NO with L-Arginine and oxygen as the reactants and NO further reacts with nucleophilic reagents to generate colored compound. Researchers may measure the absorbance at 530 nm in order to calculate the activity of NOS.

II. Components of the Kit

1. For the 50T/48 Samples Kit

Reagent I: 2 bottles with 6 mL each. Can be preserved at -20°C without light for 3 months. Thaw the reagent before use and the excess reagent can be preserved at the same condition.

Reagent II: 3 vials of powder and 3 vials of liquid with 0.6mL each. Both can be preserved at -20°C for 6 months. Dissolve each vial of powder with one vial of liquid provided and the excess amount should be kept in the same condition for no more than a week. Powder with brown color can no longer be used.

Reagent III: 1 bottle of 6 mL solution. Can be preserved at 4°C without light for 3 months.

Reagent IV: 1 bottle of 3 mL solution. Kept at RT for 6 months. Warm the solution at 37°C were the solution frozen at low temperature.

Reagent V: 2 bottles with 60 mL each. Can be preserved at 4°C for 6 months. Warm the solution at 37°C till clear were the solution appears turbidity.

2. For the 25T/24 Samples Kit

Only one bottle of reagent is provided for both reagent I and V. As for reagent III and IV, the volumes of the solutions are halved while the amount of reagent II provided remains the same.

III. Procedures

	Blank Tube	Sample Tube(s)
Double Distilled Water (DDW, μL)	A*	
Sample(s) (μL)		A*
Reagent I (μL)	200	200
Reagent II Solution (μL)	10	10
Reagent III (μL)	100	100
Mix thoroughly and warm at 37°C for 15 min in the water bath		
Reagent IV (μL)	100	100
Reagent V (μL)	2000	2000

Mix thoroughly. Zero the cuvettes with DDW and record the optical density of each tube at 530 nm.

Notes:

1. A is an arbitrary number and the recommended values are 50-100, 30, 50, 30 and 100 for rat hepatic homogenate, mouse serum, rat renal homogenate, canine serum and myocardial medium respectively.
2. Before spectrophotometric measurement, no crystal or turbidity is allowed in the cuvettes. Under such circumstance, warm at 37°C till clear before the measurement.

IV. Calculation

A. NOS activities in serum

1. Definition

One activity unit is defined as 1 nmol NO generated in 1 mL serum per min.

2. Formula

$$\begin{aligned} \text{T - NOS Activity} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{Nanomolar Attenuation Coefficient}} \times \frac{V_{\text{total}}}{V_{\text{sample}}} \times \frac{1}{\text{Path Length} \times T} \div 1000 \\ \text{U/mL} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{38.3 \times 10^{-6}} \times \frac{2.41 + A}{A} \times \frac{1}{1 \times 15} \div 1000 \end{aligned}$$

3. Example

30µL serum was measured and the OD values were 0.021 and 0.287 for blank and sample tube respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{T - NOS Activity} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{Nanomolar Attenuation Coefficient}} \times \frac{V_{\text{total}}}{V_{\text{sample}}} \times \frac{1}{\text{Path Length} \times T} \div 1000 \\ \text{U/mL} &= \frac{0.287 - 0.021}{38.3 \times 10^{-6}} \times \frac{2.41 + 0.03}{0.03} \times \frac{1}{1 \times 15} \div 1000 = 37.66 \text{U/mL} \end{aligned}$$

B. NOS activities in tissue

1. Definition

One activity unit is defined as 1 nmol NO generated in 1 mg tissue proteins per min.

2. Formula

$$\begin{aligned} \text{T - NOS Activity} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{Nanomolar Attenuation Coefficient}} \times \frac{V_{\text{total}}}{V_{\text{sample}}} \times \frac{1}{\text{Path Length} \times T} \div \frac{C_{\text{Pro}}}{\text{mg/L}} \\ \text{U/mg} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{38.3 \times 10^{-6}} \times \frac{2.41 + A}{A} \times \frac{1}{1 \times 15} \div \frac{C_{\text{Pro}}}{\text{mg/L}} \end{aligned}$$

3. Example

10% rat hepatic homogenate was prepared and 50 µ L homogenate was measured accordingly with the OD values of blank and sample tubes are 0.019 and 0.202 respectively.

The protein concentration of the homogenate was 12.5mg/mL

$$\begin{aligned} \text{T - NOS Activity} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{Nanomolar Attenuation Coefficient}} \times \frac{V_{\text{total}}}{V_{\text{sample}}} \times \frac{1}{\text{Path Length} \times T} \div \frac{C_{\text{Pro}}}{\text{mg/L}} \\ \text{U/mg} &= \frac{0.202 - 0.019}{38.3 \times 10^{-6}} \times \frac{2.41 + 0.05}{0.05} \times \frac{1}{1 \times 15} \div \frac{12.5 \times 10^3}{\text{mg/L}} = 1.254 \text{U/mg} \end{aligned}$$

V. Notes

1. Reagent II solution is recommended to be used right after its preparation or otherwise
2. NOS is not stable with slow catalytic rate and the samples should be kept frozen at -20°C if not measured.
3. Reagent I and II should not be repeated freezing and thawing.